

Reference letter of a prestigious university professor

I have known and worked with Dr Javier Perez-Barbera for over 20 years. He first came to work with me at the Macaulay Land Use Research Institute under a post-doctoral fellowship. Javier then transferred to become an employee of the Institute, firstly under my line-management, and then as an independent scientist.

In the past 20 years Javier and I have published seventeen scientific publications in a range of high impact journals (e.g. PLOS, Proceedings of the Royal Society, Evolution). Javier is first author on the majority of these publications. Our joint research span a broad range of subject areas, including ecology, evolution, nutrition and behaviour of large mammalian herbivores. I have no doubt that these publications would not have come to fruition without Javier's significant input into data collection and analysis. In fact, Javier, designed a number of new statistical methodologies and data collection techniques over the period of our collaboration.

In my view Javier is an exceptional research scientist. He is one of my most valued colleagues and I have been proud to have been involved in his research career. He is very able to develop new research ideas and he is highly skilled at designing equipment to gather data. Javier is extremely engaging and quick to seize opportunities to collaborate and develop new areas of research. He is also committed to training young researchers and has supervised a large number of undergraduate and postgraduate students from Spain under the Global Training and Leonardo da Vinci programmes. I know that he is a highly valued supervisor and commits significant time to ensuring that students are well trained.

In regard to the contribution that the Beatriz Galindo Program can make to Javier's career – there is no doubt in my mind that Javier can and is operating at the level of University Professor. Beatriz Galindo Program is a great opportunity for him to consolidate his career in his country of origin. He will make the most of the opportunity and will be a credit to Beatriz Galindo Program and the University of Castilla-La Mancha.

Please, do not hesitate to contact me for further assistance

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